

OPTIMIZATION OF THE PROCEDURE FOR TAXATION OF PERSONAL INCOME

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Abstract: *The article presents important aspects of the structure of total income of individuals and the optimization of the tax regime.*

Keywords: *individual, property income, taxation, income tax.*

The Strategy of Action for the Development of the Republic, approved by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, identifies the third priority area for the further development and liberalization of the economy. At the same time, the issues of increasing real incomes of the population are always in the center of attention of our state, contribute to the growth of real incomes in the context of an increase in nominal incomes of the population, the stability of prices for consumer goods [1].

At the current stage of the development of tax theory, it is necessary to pay special attention to the effect of taxation, since their consequences can lead to more likely consequences for society and to the fact that from the very beginning there can be no clear forecast. One of the main results of taxation is the "income effect," when taxes inherently withdraw part of the income of individuals by redistribution, which, in turn, affects the amount of real income (including the consumer and accumulative norm) at the disposal of the next individual from whom the tax was paid.

The composition of the income of the population and the composition of taxable income in our country differ from each other. According to the current tax legislation,

the composition of the total income of individuals on taxation is as follows.

Income in the form of remuneration, property income, income in the form of material payment and other income. According to labor contracts or civil law contracts that are the subject of work and services, all payments belonging to individuals relate to income in the form of remuneration. Income as remuneration includes incentive payments established in accordance with tax legislation, compensation and income received by an individual from payment of non-working time. The property income of individuals includes interest received, dividend income, income from rental of property and income from the sale of property owned by individuals on the right of private ownership.

The diversity of the composition of the income of the population requires the introduction of differentiated tax relations with such income. In this regard, when taxing the income of individuals in the republic, benefits are provided for most income received from household farming, or in the order of inheritance or donation, except for monetary rewards paid to heirs of works of science, literature and art, performers of works of literature and art, as well as authors of discoveries, inventions and industrial designs, as well as collected money and funds [2].

Analysis of the level of inequality in the size of post-tax income can lead to errors, since it is unclear what factors caused these inequality, and indirect taxes on consumer goods change consumers' price and consumer structures. This, in turn, will lead to a change in the key indicators of the consumer price index when translating nominal income into real income. Based on the above considerations, the utility function can be expressed as follows:

$$U = f(x_1, \dots, x_n, L) \quad (1)$$

where U – usefulness; x_i – commodity consumption, including future consumption depending on the current fund; L – the amount of labor offered.

Only the total volume of consumption, expressed in real income (Y) after taxes, is important, and the utility function has the following form:

$$U = f(Y, L) \quad (2)$$

It is recommended to provide tax (income tax) on the income of individuals levied on the income of an individual using the economic model.

Despite the fact that today the discussion of approaches to establishing the procedure for taxing personal income is relevant, tax legislation and taxation mechanisms are being improved, often the establishment of effective rates and changes in personal income tax rates are extremely ambiguous, and when taxing personal income in various ways they become more vulnerable. The problem of the influence of the taxation method on the economic condition of an individual is especially urgent [3].

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